

**Prediction of binaural speech intelligibility in noise and reverberation for
normal-hearing and hearing-impaired listeners**

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1 A binaural model is proposed to predict speech intelligibility for normal-hearing (NH)
2 and hearing-impaired listeners in rooms. It combines two existing models. The
3 *leclere2015* model takes binaural room impulse responses (BRIRs) as inputs and ac-
4 counts for the temporal smearing of the speech by reverberation, but only works with
5 stationary noises for NH listeners. The *vicente2020* model takes the speech and noise
6 signals at the ears as well as the listener audiogram as inputs and accounts for mod-
7 ulations in the noise and hearing loss, but cannot predict for the temporal smearing
8 of the speech by reverberation. The new model takes the audiogram, BRIRs and ear
9 signals as inputs to account for the temporal smearing of the speech, the masker mod-
10 ulations and hearing loss. Its predictions corresponded well to the speech reception
11 thresholds measured in seven experiments from the literature. The proposed model
12 can predict a much larger range of conditions than the two previous models without
13 any loss of accuracy. In terms of model parameters, four methods were compared
14 to separate the early and late reverberation, which was a model parameter, and two
15 methods were compared to account for hearing loss.

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16 I. INTRODUCTION

17 Hearing-impaired (HI) listeners often complain about difficulties to understand speech in
18 noisy and reverberant rooms. The aim of the present study was to develop a model able to
19 predict their ability to understand speech in such environments.

20 One key mechanism to understand speech in noisy environments is spatial release from
21 masking (SRM), the ability to benefit from a difference in position between the target
22 speech and noise masker sources (Bronkhorst and Plomp, 1988). It can be separated in two
23 mechanisms, better-ear listening and binaural unmasking. Better-ear listening originates
24 from differences of interaural level differences (ILDs) between the target and masker signals
25 at the two ears, which results in differences of signal-to-noise ratio (SNR) at the two ears,
26 allowing us to benefit from the better SNR between the two ears to better understand the
27 target speech. Binaural unmasking relies on the differences of interaural time differences
28 (ITD) produced by the target and masker. It can be modeled by assuming that the listener
29 is able to equalize the masker at the two ears, and partially cancel it to improve intelligibility
30 (Durlach, 1963). SRM is usually reduced for HI listeners (Glyde *et al.*, 2011). First, their
31 elevated hearing thresholds decrease the audibility of the speech signal, which can limit the
32 benefit of better-ear listening (since the speech signal at the better ear may not be audible).
33 Second, they have a reduced sensitivity to the temporal fine structure of sounds (Füllgrabe
34 and Moore, 2017), which might slightly limit their ability for binaural unmasking (Vicente
35 *et al.*, 2021).

36 Room reverberation has several detrimental effects on speech intelligibility in noise.
37 It temporally smears the target speech, which degrades its intelligibility (Houtgast and
38 Steeneken, 1985). Reverberation also temporally smears the masker. This can be detrimen-
39 tal to intelligibility when the masker is modulated in amplitude, as it reduces the intelligibil-
40 ity benefit coming from listening in the “dips” of the masker, also called dip listening benefit
41 (Festen and Plomp, 1990; Miller and Licklider, 1950). SRM is also reduced by reverberation
42 (Plomp, 1976). Sound reflections travelling around the head reduce ILDs, impairing better-
43 ear listening. These reflections also decorrelate the sound at the two ears, reducing binaural
44 unmasking (Lavandier and Culling, 2008). The sensitivity of HI listeners to reverberation
45 has been a matter of debate. They seem to be as much affected as normal-hearing (NH)
46 listeners by the effects of reverberation on the speech and the masker in monaural conditions
47 (Cueille *et al.*, 2022). There is some evidence that this is also the case in binaural conditions
48 (Helfer and Wilber, 1990; Xia *et al.*, 2018).

49 Several binaural speech intelligibility models have been proposed in the literature (for a
50 review, see Lavandier and Best, 2020). Most predict SRM and the effects of reverberation on
51 SRM. Some of these models can also predict the degradation of speech intelligibility caused
52 by reverberation temporally smearing the target speech but only for NH listeners (Leclère
53 *et al.*, 2015; van Wijngaarden and Drullman, 2008). Others models allow predictions for HI
54 listeners (Beutelmann and Brand, 2006; Beutelmann *et al.*, 2010; Vicente *et al.*, 2020), but
55 cannot account for the temporal smearing of the target speech by reverberation. Rennies
56 *et al.* (2011) developed three extensions of the model proposed by Beutelmann *et al.* (2010).
57 Those extensions allow to predict speech intelligibility with HI listeners and temporally

58 smeared speech. [Rennies *et al.* \(2019\)](#) also proposed a fourth extension which allows to
59 predict speech intelligibility in conditions where the later reflections of the target speech
60 can be useful to intelligibility. However, to the best of our knowledge, these model versions
61 were only tested for NH listeners and a stationary noise masker. [Andersen *et al.* \(2016,](#)
62 [2018\)](#) proposed binaural models based on those of [Taal *et al.* \(2011\)](#) and [Beutelmann *et al.*](#)
63 [\(2010\)](#). The models of [Andersen *et al.* \(2016, 2018\)](#) can predict the performances of NH
64 listeners in reverberant conditions, and the effect of non-linear speech processing similar to
65 those used in hearing aids. However, nothing is currently implemented so that they could
66 predict the effect of hearing loss. During the Clarity Prediction Challenge ([Barker *et al.*,](#)
67 [2022](#)), several binaural models using a machine learning approach were tested on datasets
68 involving HI listeners and signals processed by different speech enhancement algorithms. In
69 principle, these models are able to do predictions for HI listeners wearing hearing aids in
70 rooms. However, the more accurate models require being trained with speech and conditions
71 very similar to the evaluation material beforehand.

72 A new model was developed here, combining the models of [Vicente *et al.* \(2020\)](#) and
73 [Leclère *et al.* \(2015\)](#), to predict the speech reception thresholds (SRTs, the SNRs for 50%
74 intelligibility) in non-stationary noise for NH and HI listeners in binaural and reverberant
75 conditions. Using datasets from the literature described in more details below, this model
76 is shown to account for SRM and the influence of reverberation on SRM, dip listening and
77 the influence of reverberation on dip listening, temporal smearing of the target speech by
78 reverberation, and hearing loss.

79 II. DESCRIPTION OF THE MODELS

80 A. Original models

81 Both the [Vicente *et al.* \(2020\)](#) and [Leclère *et al.* \(2015\)](#) models (*vicente2020* and
82 *leclere2015* in the following and in [Lavandier *et al.* \(2022\)](#)) are based on a model de-
83 veloped by [Lavandier and Culling \(2010\)](#). This model allows to predict better-ear listening
84 and binaural unmasking advantages by frequency bands, taking the signals recorded at the
85 ears of the listener as inputs. Instead of the target speech, the target signal consists of
86 a speech-shaped noise with the long-term characteristics of the target speech (magnitude
87 spectrum and ITD). This is done in order to avoid that the short pauses between words lead
88 to very low SNRs. Better-ear listening is implemented by evaluating the SNR at each ear by
89 frequency band. The maximum SNR across ears is integrated across frequency using a SII
90 weighting ([ANSI S3.5, 1997](#)) to obtain a broadband target-to-interferer ratio. The binaural
91 unmasking advantage is computed in each frequency band following a formula proposed by
92 [Culling *et al.* \(2005\)](#), and integrated across bands using the SII weightings. The binaural
93 unmasking advantage and better-ear ratio are summed in order to obtain a binaural ratio.
94 The binaural ratio is a value in dB which reflects speech intelligibility. A higher binaural
95 ratio represents a better speech intelligibility. Differences in binaural ratios can be compared
96 to differences in SRTs. To be compared to absolute SRTs, a reference need to be chosen,
97 which is often the average SRT measured in the experiment ([Lavandier *et al.*, 2022](#)).

98 The *leclere2015* model is an extension of the [Lavandier and Culling \(2010\)](#) model based on
99 the concept of useful-to-detrimental ratio ([Lochner and Burger, 1964](#)). It takes the binaural

100 room impulse responses (BRIRs) at the ears of the listener as input. The target BRIR is
101 separated into an early and a late part. The early part is considered as useful for speech
102 intelligibility, while the late part is considered as detrimental and is concatenated with
103 the masker BRIR. The early-late separation can be done using several temporal window
104 shapes: rectangular, linear, sigmoid (Leclère *et al.*, 2015). The *leclere2015* model uses
105 “linear” windows: the early window starts with a constant amplitude of 1, followed by a
106 linear decrease to 0, while the late window starts at 0 and then increases linearly to 1, so
107 that the two windows sum to 1 at each instant. These linear windows are defined by two
108 parameters. The early-late limit (ELL) defines the duration of the constant portion in the
109 windows. The decay duration defines the duration of the linear decrease/increase. Even if
110 Leclère *et al.* (2015) found that the best model performances were obtained when these two
111 parameters were room-dependent, the *leclere2015* model uses a room-independent ELL and
112 decay duration, fixed to 30 ms and 25 ms, respectively (Leclère *et al.*, 2015). These values
113 were shown to be the best compromise solution when these parameters are fixed across
114 rooms/positions. This model accounts for the detrimental effects of reverberation on the
115 target speech and SRM for stationary noises. However, because it does not take the masker
116 signal and the listener’s audiogram as inputs, it cannot predict the effects of the masker
117 modulations and hearing impairment.

118 The *vicente2020* model is a different extension of the Lavandier and Culling (2010) model
119 with two main improvements: a short-term analysis to take into account the effect of masker
120 modulations (Collin and Lavandier, 2013), and an internal noise modelling the effect of
121 hearing impairment (Vicente *et al.*, 2020). Its structure is shown on the right part of Figure

1. It takes the target and masker signals at the ears of the listener as inputs. The target signal is a speech-shaped noise with the long-term characteristics of the target speech. The masker signal is segmented in time frames and the better-ear ratio and binaural unmasking advantage are calculated by frequency bands in each time frame (Collin and Lavandier, 2013). An internal noise spectrum is also implemented at each ear, with spectrum levels depending on the listener audiogram and the external sound broadband level. Vicente *et al.* (2020) approximated this external sound level with the masker level, assuming that the broadband SNR is below 0 dB. The masker and target signals need to be calibrated to the external sound level. When calculating the better-ear SNR, the SNR at each ear is computed using the higher level between the internal noise and the external masker. The binaural unmasking advantage is computed as done by Lavandier and Culling (2010), except that it is set to zero as soon as the target or masker level is below the internal noise level at one ear. The *vicente2020* model allows to predict SRM for NH and HI listeners. However, because it does not consider the early and late parts of the target separately (and thus considers them both useful), it cannot account for the temporal smearing of the target by reverberation.

B. Proposed model

1. Model structure

The model proposed here is a combination of the *vicente2020* and *leclere2015* models. Its structure is presented on Figure 1. It consists in applying the *vicente2020* model on

142 inputs prepared following the *leclere2015* approach, as also done in one of the models of
143 [Rennies et al. \(2011\)](#). Instead of using the target and masker signals at the ear, the original
144 speech and noise materials and the BRIRs at the ears are taken as inputs. This allows to
145 re-create the stimuli used in the experiments, except that the early and late targets can
146 be separated. This cannot be done with only the stimuli at the ears. The target BRIR is
147 separated in an early and a late part as in the *leclere2015* model. The speech material is
148 averaged across sentences and the average target signal is convolved with the early and the
149 late target BRIR. The early target signal is taken as input in the *vicente2020* model, as the
150 useful signal. The late target signal is summed with the masker signal, that is to say the
151 noise material convolved with the masker BRIR. The resulting signal is taken as input in
152 the *vicente2020* model, as the detrimental signal.

153 In order to predict the effect of hearing loss, two different methods were tested here to
154 calculate the internal noise level. The first method was the one used in the *vicente2020*
155 model, where the internal noise depends on the listener audiogram and the external sound
156 broadband level. In the second method, this broadband level is replaced by the external
157 sound spectrum, so that the internal noise level in a given frequency band depends on
158 the external sound level in that particular band rather than on its broadband level. This
159 modification influences the predictions only for HI listeners (i.e. here the datasets from
160 [Cueille et al. \(2022\)](#) and [Vicente et al. \(2021\)](#)).

161 The processing of the signals and BRIRs is detailed in Figure 2. After convolution with
162 the BRIRs, the target and masker signals need to be calibrated to the presentation level,
163 corresponding to the sound level at which the stimuli were played during the experiment.

FIG. 1: Structure of the proposed model. The first block represents the signal processing (detailed in Figure 2). The second block represents the *vicente2020* model

FIG. 2: Processing of the signals and BRIRs in the proposed model

164 This level was approximated as the masker level here, due to the masker signal usually
 165 having a fixed level higher than the target level in the experiments considered. In the
 166 proposed model, the calibration of the early and late target signals necessitates that they
 167 are multiplied by the gain required to calibrate the level of the “full” target (the average of
 168 the speech sentences convolved with the “full” target BRIR) to the presentation level.

169 **2. Choice of the early-late limit**

170 Leclère *et al.* (2015) tested several shapes for the temporal windows used to do the early-
171 late separation and showed that they led to very similar results. Here only linear windows
172 (as used in the room-independent model *leclere2015*) were considered. Both the ELL and
173 the decay duration can be varied to improve the model performances, so that for a given
174 decay duration an ELL can be found to reach optimal performance (Leclère *et al.*, 2015).
175 Here, it was decided to only vary the ELL and keep the decay duration at a fixed value of 25
176 ms (the default value used in the *leclere2015* model), except when the computation method
177 required another decay duration value (see the Kokabi method below). Four methods of
178 ELL computation were tested.

179 First, a room-independent ELL fixed at 30 ms (as in *leclere2015*) was tested. The corre-
180 sponding model version was called “model-RI” (Room-Independent).

181 The second approach was based on the mixing time. The ELL was set to the physical
182 mixing time defined as the moment when the diffuse reverberation tail begins (Lindau *et al.*,
183 2012). It was estimated using the method proposed by Abel and Huang (2006), based on the
184 calculation of the echo density profile of each BRIR, meaning that the ELL is room/position-
185 dependent. To calculate the echo density, a rectangular time window of 23 ms slides along
186 the target BRIR. Within each time window, the standard deviation of the sound pressure is
187 calculated. The proportion of samples outside the interval “mean window value \pm window
188 standard deviation” is calculated. The echo density is defined in each time window as
189 the ratio between this proportion and the proportion of samples which would be outside

190 the window standard deviation if the samples followed a Gaussian distribution. At the
191 beginning of the BRIR, the sound pressure equals zero, so the echo density is also zero. As
192 time increases the sound becomes diffuse and the sound pressure of the BRIR within the
193 time window starts to resemble a Gaussian distribution, so that the echo density tends to
194 one. The physical mixing time ELL is defined as the instant when the echo density reaches
195 unity. The version of the model using this ELL was called “model-Abel”.

196 The third model version varied the ELL depending on the BRIR interaural cross-
197 correlation (IACC) based on a linear regression proposed by Kokabi *et al.* (2018), in a
198 first attempt to develop a room-dependent version of *leclere2015*. They used *leclere2015*
199 on BRIRs simulated by Rennies *et al.* (2011) (1 room, 4 distances, 2 source positions), as
200 well as BRIRs from a simulated room with varying absorption coefficients (4 absorption
201 coefficients). To predict the SRTs of Rennies *et al.* (2011) and those measured in their
202 own study, *leclere2015* was tested with several ELLs, and a linear regression was done in
203 order to find a correlation between the ELLs leading to the best predicted SRTs and the
204 IACCs. The regression $ELL = 143 - 202 \times IACC$ gave the best results, with a correlation
205 coefficient of 0.74. This ELL computation was tested here. It was developed with a 1-ms
206 decay duration, and the same decay duration value was thus used here. This version of the
207 model was called “model-Kokabi”.

208 The fourth method to compute the ELL was based on the BRIR short-term IACC. The
209 similarity of the reflections at the two ears is used to decide whether they are detrimental,
210 assuming that reverberation makes the late target more masking when it is more different
211 at the ears thus limiting binaural unmasking (Lavandier and Culling, 2008; Leclère *et al.*,

212 2015; Rennie *et al.*, 2019). It is based on the work of Rennie *et al.* (2019), who showed
213 that reflections might be defined as useful or detrimental depending on whether they are
214 useful/detrimental for SRM and binaural intelligibility, rather than whether they are early
215 or late. Here the IACC was measured in rectangular temporal windows of 23 ms. The ELL
216 was defined as the instant when the short-term IACC first becomes inferior to 0.6. This value
217 was arbitrarily chosen to test the concept, but the estimated ELLs were very similar when
218 it was chosen between 0.7 and 0.5. This version of the model was called “model-IACC”.

219 C. Model evaluation

220 The eight versions of the proposed model, corresponding to the four computations of EEL
221 and the two computations of internal noise, were evaluated using the data from seven exper-
222 iments. The first experiment of Lavandier *et al.* (2012) was used to consider the influence
223 of reverberation on SRM (for stationary noise and NH listeners). The third experiment of
224 Lavandier and Culling (2008) was selected to involve the influence of reverberation on SRM
225 and the temporal smearing of the target (for stationary noise and NH listeners). The first
226 experiment of Collin and Lavandier (2013) was chosen to involve the effect of reverberation
227 on dip listening (for frontal sources generating limited binaural effects, and NH listeners).
228 The third experiment of Collin and Lavandier (2013) allowed to consider the dip listening
229 benefit and the temporal smearing of the target by reverberation (for frontal sources gen-
230 erating limited binaural effects, and NH listeners). The fourth experiment of Collin and
231 Lavandier (2013) was used to combine the effects of dip listening and SRM, even if only
232 at a low reverberation level (for NH listeners). The experiment of Cueille *et al.* (2022) was

233 chosen to involve the effects of reverberation on the temporal smearing of the target for NH
234 and HI listeners (in monaural conditions). The dataset 1 of [Vicente *et al.* \(2021\)](#) allows to
235 test the influence of reverberation on SRM for stationary and modulated noises, with NH
236 and HI listeners.

237 Overall, the models were tested on data measured in four different labs, with four differ-
238 ent speech material, two languages, using four different procedures. The experiments from
239 [Lavandier *et al.* \(2012\)](#) and [Lavandier and Culling \(2008\)](#) were adaptive SRT measurements
240 done at the Cardiff University (UK) with unpredictable English sentences from the Har-
241 vard Sentence List ([IEEE, 1969](#)). The experiments from [Collin and Lavandier \(2013\)](#) were
242 adaptive SRT measurements done at ENTPE (France), with unpredictable French sentences
243 from an open set developed by [Raake and Katz \(2006\)](#). The experiment from [Cueille *et al.*](#)
244 [\(2022\)](#) was done at CRNL (France) and measured full psychometric functions, with French
245 sentences from a closed set matrix-type speech material ([Jansen *et al.*, 2012](#)). The dataset
246 from [Vicente *et al.* \(2021\)](#) involves adaptative SRT measurements done at Macquarie Uni-
247 versity (Australia), with English sentences from an open set speech material ([Bench *et al.*,](#)
248 [1979](#)).

249 The predicted SRTs were compared with the measured data, and with the predictions
250 of the *leclere2015* and *vicente2020* models (only showed in the supplementary materials¹
251 for figure legibility). The four ELL calculation methods were tested for all datasets, except
252 the one from [Cueille *et al.* \(2022\)](#). The Kokabi and IACC versions could not be tested
253 with this dataset because the stimuli are monaural. The two methods of internal noise
254 calculation were only compared with the two datasets involving HI listeners, as the internal

255 noise does not affect the predictions for NH listeners. For each dataset and for all model
256 versions, the Pearson’s correlation coefficient between the average measured and predicted
257 SRTs was calculated, along with the mean and largest absolute errors between average
258 data and predictions. Furthermore, the individual predictions of the HI listeners are shown
259 in the supplementary materials for the two datasets involving HI listeners, along with the
260 Pearson correlation coefficient between the individual measured and predicted SRTs and the
261 mean and largest absolute errors between individual data and prediction across conditions.
262 The individual predictions of the NH listeners were not shown, as the models give very
263 similar predictions for the NH listeners due to not having other individual inputs than
264 the audiograms. Thus they cannot predict the individual variability of the NH listeners
265 ([Lavandier *et al.*, 2021](#)).

266 **D. Implementation of the predictions**

267 Depending on the dataset the target signal was created by averaging between 60 and
268 280 sentence waveforms. The datasets involving only NH listeners did not give information
269 on the presentation level used during data collection. The presentation level was fixed at
270 65 dB SPL for these datasets. This did not affect the predictions as the presentation level
271 only affects the model through the internal noise that has an effect for the predictions of
272 HI listeners. When the audiograms of the NH listeners were unavailable, their hearing
273 thresholds were fixed at 0 dB HL at all frequencies.

274 To compare absolute SRTs and binaural ratios (the model output), a reference needs to
275 be chosen (it does not influence the relative differences in predictions across conditions). The

276 average measured SRT within each dataset was chosen as reference (Collin and Lavandier,
277 2013; Lavandier and Culling, 2010; Lavandier *et al.*, 2012). Before comparison to the mea-
278 sured data, the binaural ratios were inverted (higher ratios reflect better intelligibility and
279 lower SRTs). Inverted binaural ratios were offset by subtracting their mean and adding the
280 corresponding average SRT across conditions and listeners (the reference), thus aligning the
281 inverted binaural ratios with the measured SRTs. The *leclere2015* and *vicente2020* models,
282 implemented and made available by Lavandier *et al.* (2022), were used here using the same
283 assumptions (whenever relevant).

284 III. DATASETS USED TO TEST THE MODELS AND RESULTS OF THE PRE- 285 DICATIONS

286 The datasets involved only NH listeners, unless otherwise specified. The model versions
287 based on the external broadband level and spectrum level give identical predictions for NH
288 listeners, so that four model versions are compared. For the datasets with HI listeners,
289 the difference in internal noise implementation leads to eight tested model versions. The
290 performance statistics for the different model versions are shown in Table I. The estimated
292 ELL obtained with the four ELL separation methods can be found in Table II.

293 A. Lavandier et al. (2012)

294 In the experiment 1 of Lavandier *et al.* (2012), the stimuli were convolved with BRIRs
295 measured in a real room and spectral envelope impulse responses (SEIRs). The SEIRs
296 were obtained by removing the temporal characteristics of the BRIRs, in order to remove

TABLE I: Pearson correlation coefficient, mean and largest errors obtained with the four versions of the proposed model with the internal noise depending on the external sound broadband level, as well as those of the two existing models (*vicente2020* and *leclere2015*), and those of the models versions taking the external sound spectrum as input presented in bold font (only for the datasets for which this change affects the predictions)

Dataset	model-RI	model-Abel	model-Kokabi	model-IACC	vicente2020	leclere2015
Lavandier et al. (2012)	0.98	0.98	0.97	0.98	0.95	0.97
	0.2dB	0.2dB	0.3dB	0.2dB	0.4dB	0.3dB
	0.6dB	0.6dB	0.8dB	0.7dB	0.6dB	0.9dB
Lavandier and Culling (2008)	0.85	0.87	0.8	0.85	0.48	0.86
	0.8dB	0.8dB	1dB	1.8dB	1.2dB	0.8dB
	1.4dB	1.3dB	1.9dB	4.2dB	2.3dB	1.3dB
Collin and Lavandier (2013) Exp.1	0.87	0.87	0.89	0.87	0.85	0.49
	0.4dB	0.4dB	0.3dB	0.4dB	0.5dB	0.6dB
	1.2dB	1.2dB	0.90dB	1.1dB	1.3dB	1.5dB
Collin and Lavandier (2013) Exp.3	0.99	0.99	0.86	0.99	0.58	0.97
	1.1dB	0.3dB	3dB	1dB	3.6dB	3.1dB
	1.4dB	0.7dB	3.6dB	1.4	4.5dB	3.4dB
Collin and Lavandier (2013) Exp.4	0.91	0.91	0.93	0.91	0.93	0.87
	0.6dB	0.6dB	0.4dB	0.5dB	0.6dB	0.7dB
	1.4dB	1.5dB	0.9dB	1.4dB	1.4dB	1.8dB
Cueille et al. (2022)	0.95/ 0.93	0.89/ 0.87	N/A	N/A	0.59	0.73
	1.4dB/ 0.9dB	1.5dB/ 1.2dB			2.4dB	2dB
	3dB/ 2.4dB	3.6dB/ 3dB			6.1dB	3.7dB/
Vicente et al. (2021)	0.93/ 0.87	0.93/ 0.88	0.92/ 0.87	0.93/ 0.87	0.92	0.39
	0.9dB/ 1.1dB	0.9dB/ 1.1dB	0.9dB/ 1.1dB	0.9dB/ 1.1dB	0.9dB	1.7dB
	1.9dB/ 2.8dB	1.87dB/ 2.7dB	2.5dB/ 2.7dB	1.9dB/ 2.7dB	2dB	4.5dB

297 the ITDs while preserving the ILDs, so that better-ear listening is possible while binaural
298 unmasking is not. A single stationary noise was tested at two distances (0.65 m, “near”,
299 and 5 m, “far”) and three orientations (-25°, “left”, 0°, “front”, +25°, “right”). The target
300 speech was always at the same position (near right). The measured SRTs and predictions of

TABLE II: Estimated early-late limits (in ms) of the three room-dependent model versions for the seven tested datasets with the three room-dependent model versions. Each line corresponds to a target BRIR. Datasets are separated by double lines.

Target BRIR	Abel	Kokabi	IACC
LAV12:BRIR	37	6	11
LAV12:SEIR	42(end)	0	11
LAV08:1	243(end)	0	12
LAV08:07	243(end)	12	11
LAV08:05	26	49	0
LAV08:02	21	26	0
COL13:exp1	23	0	11
COL13:exp3-065	25	22	11
COL13:exp3-1000	14	104	0
COL13:exp4	32	0	11
CUE22:0.15	65	N/A	N/A
CUE22:0.5	70	N/A	N/A
CUE22:0.8	75	N/A	N/A
CUE22:1.1	39	N/A	N/A
CUE22:1.5	50	N/A	N/A
VIC21:+20	243(end)	0	5
VIC21:+40	243(end)	0	5
VIC21:-90	243(end)	0	5

301 the four versions of the proposed model can be found in Figure 3. The SRM is highlighted
302 by comparing the SRTs in the left and front conditions to those in the co-located condition
303 (near right). An interaction between reverberation and SRM was also observed, as there
304 was less SRM in the far conditions.

305 The four versions of the model give similarly accurate predictions. The Kokabi and IACC
306 versions slightly overestimate the SRTs in the BRIRs conditions and underestimate them in

FIG. 3: Mean SRTs with standard errors across listeners measured by Lavandier *et al.*

(2012). Predicted SRTs are displayed for the proposed model with four ELL calculation methods.

307 the SEIRs conditions. The performance statistics in Table I do not reflect these differences
 308 (which remain lower than 1 dB) and show similar accuracy for the four versions. It is
 309 interesting to note that even though their predictions are similar, the four model versions
 310 estimate different ELLs for this dataset. As can be seen in the Table II, the Abel version
 311 considered the whole target BRIR as useful (as the echo density never reached 1), while the
 312 Kokabi and IACC versions estimated an ELL lower than the room-independent ELL at 30
 313 ms.

314 As expected, *vicente2020* and *leclere2015* accurately predict this dataset (Suppl. Fig.
 315 1¹) and give performance statistics similar to the proposed model.

316 **B. Lavandier and Culling (2008)**

317 In the experiment 3 of Lavandier and Culling (2008), a single stationary noise was always
318 spatially separated from the target speech, the noise being 65° to the left of the listener
319 and the target being 65° to its right. The room absorption coefficients used for the target
320 and noise were controlled separately for each source, testing four coefficients: 1, 0.7, 0.5,
321 0.2. The measured SRTs and model predictions are shown in Figure 4. The SRT increase
322 observed as the target absorption coefficient decreases (reverberation increases) highlights
323 the temporal smearing of the target speech. The SRT increases as the masker absorption
324 coefficient decreases, highlighting the detrimental effect of reverberation on SRM.

325 The room-independent and Abel model versions give results similar to those of *leclere2015*
326 (Suppl. Fig. 2¹). They overestimate the SRT when the target absorption coefficient is 1 and
327 slightly underestimate it when it is 0.5. The Kokabi version gives similar predictions, but is
328 even less accurate when the target absorption coefficient is 0.5. The IACC version gives the
329 less accurate predictions. It underestimates the SRT when the target absorption coefficient
330 is 1 and 0.7, and largely overestimates it when it is 0.2. The performance statistics also show
331 this difference in performance, with the Kokabi and IACC versions leading to larger mean
332 and largest prediction errors. For this dataset, the Abel version considered the whole target
333 BRIR as useful for the two highest target absorption coefficients, and estimated ELLs close
334 to 30 ms for the two lowest coefficients (Table II). The Kokabi version followed an inverse
335 trend, estimating low ELLs (below 15 ms) for the highest absorption coefficient and relatively

FIG. 4: Mean SRTs with standard errors across listeners measured by Lavandier and Culling (2008). Predicted SRTs are displayed for the proposed model with four ELL calculation methods.

336 larger ELLs (49 ms and 26 ms) for the two lowest absorption coefficients. The IACC version
 337 estimated low ELLs (below 15 ms) for all conditions.

338 The *leclere2015* model has similar performance statistics as the proposed model (Table
 339 I). On the other hand, *vicente2020* is inaccurate (Suppl. Fig. 2¹). This is expected, as
 340 *vicente2020* does not take the target BRIR as input and cannot predict the effect of the
 341 temporal smearing of the target speech.

342 C. Collin and Lavandier (2013) - Experiment 1

343 In the experiment 1 of Collin and Lavandier (2013), SRTs were measured with stationary
 344 noise or noise modulated by the envelope of a speech signal comprised of one, two or four

345 voices. The interferer was tested at three distances (65, 125, and 500 cm) in front of the lis-
346 tener in a lecture hall. Increasing its distance increased the relative amount of reverberation
347 for the interferer. The target was always at 65 cm in front of the listener. The measured
348 SRTs and model predictions can be found in Figure 5. A dip listening benefit is observed, as
349 the SRTs are lower when the masker is modulated. This dip listening benefit is reduced by
350 reverberation when the interferer distance increases. Note that room coloration also made
351 the noises less masking when their distance increased, counterbalancing the reduction of
352 dip listening for the modulated noises (for more discussion on this effect, see [Collin and](#)
353 [Lavandier \(2013\)](#)).

354 The four versions of the model give accurate predictions for this dataset (Table I). The
355 room-independent, Abel and IACC versions slightly underestimate the SRT in the conditions
356 with one-voice and two-voice modulated maskers, and slightly overestimate it in the con-
357 ditions with a stationary masker. In other words, the dip listening benefit appears slightly
358 overestimated. The Kokabi version is a bit more accurate in this regard. For this dataset,
359 the Abel version estimated an ELL of 23 ms, against 0 ms for the Kokabi version (that is to
360 say, the early target BRIR consisted only of the decaying part of 1 ms), and 11 ms for the
361 IACC version (Table II).

362 The *vicente2020* model predicts this dataset as accurately as the proposed model, while
363 the *leclere2015* model gives inaccurate predictions (Suppl. Fig. 3¹) with a correlation
364 between data and prediction of 0.42. This was expected as the *leclere2015* model cannot
365 predict the effect of masker modulations.

FIG. 5: Mean SRTs with standard errors across listeners measured by [Collin and Lavandier \(2013\)](#) in their first experiment. Predicted SRTs are displayed for the proposed model with four ELL calculation methods.

366 D. Collin and Lavandier (2013) - Experiment 3

367 In the experiment 3 of [Collin and Lavandier \(2013\)](#), a stationary noise and a one-voice
 368 modulated noise were tested, always close to the listener (at 65 cm). The target was tested
 369 at two distances: 65 cm and 10 m. The target and the interferer were always in front of
 370 the listener in a L-shaped room. The measured SRTs and model predictions are shown in
 371 [Figure 6](#). The temporal smearing of the target speech is highlighted by the SRT increase
 372 between the 65-cm and 10-m conditions. The dip listening benefit is highlighted by the SRT
 373 difference between the stationary and one-voice modulated masker. There was no significant
 374 interaction between the target distance and interferer modulations.

375 The Abel model version gives the best predictions, but appears to slightly overestimate
376 the SRTs at the shortest distance (65 cm) and underestimate them at the larger distance
377 (10 m), underestimating the effect of the temporal smearing of the target speech. This
378 tendency was found at a larger degree with the room-independent and Kokabi versions, the
379 Kokabi version being the worst. The performance statistics show that these two versions
380 lead to larger prediction errors (see Table I). The IACC version follows an inverse trend,
381 overestimating the temporal smearing of the target speech. For this dataset, the Abel version
382 estimated ELLs of 25 ms and 14 ms for the 65 cm and 10 m conditions, respectively. The
383 Kokabi version estimated ELLs of 22 ms and 104 ms. The IACC version estimated ELLs of
384 11 ms and 0 ms.

385 The *vicente2020* and *leclere2015* models give inaccurate predictions for this dataset
386 (Suppl. Fig. 4¹). The *vicente2020* model leads to a correlation between data and pre-
387 diction of only 0.58 and large prediction errors (Table I), because it cannot account for the
388 effect of the temporal smearing of the target speech. The *leclere2015* model provides a
389 correlation of 0.97, but also large prediction errors, because it cannot account for the effect
390 of masker modulations and dip listening.

391 E. Collin and Lavandier (2013) - Experiment 4

392 In the experiment 4 of Collin and Lavandier (2013), a stationary noise, a one-voice mod-
393 ulated noise and a two-voice modulated noise were tested. The target was always in front of
394 the listener. The stationary and two-voice modulated noises were tested in three configura-
395 tions: in front (co-located with the target), asymmetrical (+25°) and symmetrical (+25° and

FIG. 6: Mean SRTs with standard errors across listeners measured by [Collin and Lavandier \(2013\)](#) in their third experiment. Predicted SRTs are displayed for the proposed model with four ELL calculation methods.

396 -25°). The one-voice modulated noise was only tested in the co-located and asymmetrical
 397 configurations. All sources were tested at the same fixed distance (65 cm) in a meeting
 398 room (the room also used in the experiment 1 of [Lavandier et al. \(2012\)](#)). The measured
 399 SRTs and model predictions can be found in Figure 7. A dip listening benefit is observed, as
 400 the SRTs are lower with modulated interferers. SRM was also observed, as the SRTs were
 401 lower in the asymmetrical configuration compared to the co-located condition. The SRM
 402 was much reduced in the symmetrical configuration.

403 The room-independent, Abel and IACC versions show accurate predictions. They slightly
 404 overestimate the SRTs for the stationary noise, implying that the dip listening benefit is
 405 slightly overestimated. The SRTs are also underestimated for the two-voice-modulated noise

FIG. 7: Mean SRTs with standard errors across listeners measured by Collin and Lavandier (2013) in their fourth experiment. Predicted SRTs are displayed for the proposed model with four ELL calculation methods.

406 in the symmetrical configuration ($\pm 25^\circ$). The Kokabi version might provide slightly more
 407 accurate predictions, as also reflected by the performance statistics (Table I). The ELLs
 408 estimated for this dataset were 32 ms, 0 ms and 11 ms, for the Abel, Kokabi and IACC
 409 versions, respectively.

410 The *vicente2020* model accurately predicts this dataset (Table I), with performance statis-
 411 tics similar to those of the proposed model. The *leclere2015* model is able to predict the
 412 effect of spatial configuration, but not the effect of masker modulations (Suppl. Fig. 5¹).
 413 Its performance statistics are slightly worse than those of the other models.

414 **F. Cueille et al. (2022)**

415 *Cueille et al. (2022)* tested both NH and HI listeners. The HI listeners had a mean four-
416 frequency pure tone average (PTA4) of 45.2 ± 11.3 dB HL. All the stimuli were monaural.
417 A stationary noise and an unintelligible two-voice vocoded speech (as a proxy for modu-
418 lated noise) were tested. Reverberation was applied either only on the target speech (four
419 reverberation times), only on the interfering noise (one reverberation time tested), or on
420 both target and noise (one reverberation time). An anechoic condition was also tested. The
421 stimuli for the HI listeners were amplified using a linear frequency-dependant gain set with
422 the NAL-RP prescription rule (*Dillon, 2012*). The measured SRTs and the predictions from
423 the four ELL versions of the proposed model with the external broadband level as input
424 are shown in Figure 8. The scatterplots of the individual predictions are provided in the
425 supplementary material (Suppl. Fig. 10¹).

426 The effect of hearing loss can be seen with the lower SRTs of the NH listeners. The
427 effect of the temporal smearing of the speech is highlighted by the SRT increases when the
428 reverberation time used for the target speech increases. Very limited dip listening benefit
429 (difference between black and grey SRTs) was observed in the data, only for the NH listeners
430 in the less reverberant conditions. *Cueille et al. (2022)* found a larger dip listening benefit
431 at lower SNRs, considering the full psychometric curves of the listeners.

432 The Kokabi and IACC model versions could not be tested here because the stimuli are
433 monaural. The room-independent model version with an internal noise based on the broad-
434 band level can predict the global trend of the dataset, but overestimates the dip listening

435 benefit by 1 dB. The Abel version gives similar predictions, and slightly underestimates the
436 SRT variations between the conditions with low and high reverberation times, as can be
437 seen in Figure 8 thus leading to slightly lower correlation between data and predictions and
438 a larger maximum prediction error. For this dataset, the Abel version estimated large ELLs
439 (between 39 ms and 75 ms; Table II). The larger ELLs were obtained for the intermediate
440 reverberation times (0.5 s and 0.8 s), while the smaller ELLs were obtained for the highest
441 reverberation times (1.1 and 1.5 s).

442 The four ELL versions of the proposed model with the external spectrum as input are
443 shown in Figure 9. The scatterplots of the individual predictions are provided in the sup-
444plementary material (Suppl. Fig. 10¹). The model versions that use the external sound
445 broadband level (as in the *vicente2020* model) were less accurate than the versions using
446 the external sound spectrum. When focusing on the room-independent versions, taking
447 the external sound broadband level as input led to an overestimation of the SRT difference
448 between the NH and HI listeners by 3 dB (Figure 8), while the version using the external
449 sound spectrum underestimated this difference by 1 dB. This is also apparent in the individ-
450 ual predictions, where the SRTs of some listeners were largely overestimated in all conditions
451 when using the external broadband level, but not when using the external spectrum. The
452 individual performance statistics were also slightly better with the versions using the exter-
453 nal spectrum (correlation of 0.73, mean error of 3.9 dB, largest error of 16.2 dB with the
454 broadband level, and correlation of 0.75, mean error of 2.8 dB and largest error of 9.6 dB
455 with the spectrum).

FIG. 8: Mean SRTs with standard errors across listeners measured by [Cueille *et al.* \(2022\)](#). Predicted SRTs are displayed for the proposed model with the internal noise depending on the external sound broadband level, for two ELL calculation methods (the two binaural methods could not be tested with monaural stimuli).

456 The *vicente2020* and *leclere2015* models inaccurately describe this dataset (Suppl. Fig.
 457 6 and 7¹). The *vicente2020* model leads to a correlation of 0.59 and large mean and largest
 458 prediction errors, because it does not account for the temporal smearing of the target speech.
 459 The *leclere2015* model provides a correlation of 0.73 and large prediction errors, because it
 460 cannot predict the effect of hearing loss and the large differences between the SRTs of the
 461 NH and HI listeners.

FIG. 9: Same as Figure 8 but for the model versions with the internal noise depending on the external sound spectrum

462 **G. Vicente et al. (2021)**

463 *Vicente et al. (2021)* tested both NH and HI listeners. The HI listeners had a PTA4 of
 464 30.6 ± 5.8 dB HL. In the dataset 1 of their experiment, they used stationary speech-shaped
 465 noise and noise-vocoded speech as maskers. Three levels of reverberation were used for
 466 the masker, with room absorption coefficients of 1, 0.7 and 0.2. The target sentences were
 467 anechoic. The masker remained at 6.16 m of the listener, with an azimuth of 16.4° . The
 468 target sentences were simulated at 2 m of the listeners, with three tested azimuths: -90° ,
 469 20° and 40° . The stimuli of the HI listeners were amplified with the NAL-RP prescription
 470 rule. The measured SRTs and predictions from the four ELL versions of the model with

471 the external broadband level as input are shown in Figure 10. Scatterplots of the individual
472 predictions are provided in the supplementary material (Suppl Fig. 11).

473 The effect of hearing loss is highlighted with the higher SRTs of the HI listeners. The
474 dip listening benefit is highlighted with lower SRTs for the noise-vocoded speech than for
475 the speech-shaped noise. The SRM is highlighted with lower SRTs for the target azimuths
476 -90° and 40° . Increasing reverberation reduced both SRM and dip listening.

477 The four ELL separation methods give very similar predictions. The Kokabi method
478 has slightly worse performances than the other three methods, slightly underestimating the
479 SRTs at low reverberation levels. All model versions seem to overestimate the dip listening
480 benefit by about 2 dB in the condition where the room absorption coefficient is equal to 1.
481 For this dataset, the Abel version considered the whole target BRIR as useful, while the
482 Kokabi and IACC versions estimated ELLs of 0 ms and 5 ms respectively.

483 The measured SRTs and predictions from the four ELL versions of the model with the
484 external spectrum as input are shown in Figure 11. Scatterplots of the individual predictions
485 are provided in the supplementary material (Suppl. Fig. 11¹). The model versions using
486 the external spectrum are slightly less accurate than the ones using the external broadband
487 level. When focusing on the room-independent versions, using the external sound spectrum
488 led to an underestimation of the SRT difference between the NH and HI listeners by 1 dB,
489 while using the external broadband level gave accurate predictions. The two versions gave
490 similar performance statistics for the individual predictions of the HI listeners (correlation of
491 0.71, mean error of 1.5 dB, largest error of 5.3 dB with the broadband level, and correlation
492 of 0.70, mean error of 1.5 dB and largest error of 5.8 dB with the spectrum).

FIG. 10: Mean SRTs with standard errors across listeners measured by [Vicente et al. \(2021\)](#). Predicted SRTs are displayed for the proposed model with the internal noise depending on the external sound broadband level, for the internal noise depending on the external sound broadband level

493 The *vicente2020* model accurately predicts this dataset, with predictions very similar
 494 to the versions of the proposed model using the external sound broadband level (Suppl.
 495 Fig. 8¹). This is expected, as the two models are equivalent when the target speech is not
 496 temporally smeared by reverberation. The *leclere2015* model gives poor performances, as it
 497 does not take into account the effects of hearing loss and noise modulations.

FIG. 11: Same as Figure 10 but for the model versions

498 IV. DISCUSSION

499 A. Comparison of the model versions

500 The two model variations presented here are the target BRIR separation method and the
 501 internal noise calculation. The former affects the prediction of the effect of the temporal
 502 smearing of the target speech, while the later affects the prediction of the effect of hearing
 503 loss.

504 Changes in ELL affected the predictions for BRIRs with strong reverberation, but usually
 505 had little to no effect for BRIRs with little reverberation. This can be seen with the datasets
 506 from Lavandier *et al.* (2012) and Vicente *et al.* (2021) where large changes in ELL between
 507 model versions had almost no effect on the predictions. The room-independent and Abel
 508 versions gave similar results for the datasets from Lavandier and Culling (2008), and the

509 first and fourth experiments of [Collin and Lavandier \(2013\)](#). They differed only for two
510 datasets. For the third experiment of [Collin and Lavandier \(2013\)](#), the Abel version was more
511 accurate, while the room-independent version underestimated the effect of reverberation on
512 the target. For the experiment of [Cueille *et al.* \(2022\)](#), the room-independent version was
513 more accurate, with the Abel version slightly underestimating the effect of reverberation
514 on the target. For this dataset the ELL estimated with the Abel version increased for
515 intermediate reverberation times and decreased for high reverberation times, contrarily to
516 the other datasets where the ELL varied monotonously with the reverberation level. In this
517 experiment the room was virtual, created with the ray-tracing software CATT-Acoustic.
518 The generation of the BRIRs is done with a random projection of rays across the room,
519 a stochastic process. This could explain why the ELLs do not vary monotonously, as the
520 exact pattern of reflections randomly changes between BRIRs.

521 The Kokabi version was less accurate than the other versions with the datasets involving
522 high levels of reverberation, that is to say, [Lavandier and Culling \(2008\)](#) and the third
523 experiment of [Collin and Lavandier \(2013\)](#). This is in accordance with the conclusions of
524 [Kokabi *et al.* \(2018\)](#), who developed their linear regression based on long-term IACC at
525 low and intermediate reverberation levels only. Our results indicate that the efficiency of
526 this regression decreases at high levels of reverberation. It is interesting to note that this
527 model version gave slightly better predictions than the others at very low reverberation
528 levels, that is to say in some conditions of the first and fourth experiments of [Collin and](#)
529 [Lavandier \(2013\)](#). This could suggest that the linear regression might be appropriate for low
530 reverberation levels. Alternatively it could indicate that using a shorter decay duration is

531 more relevant then. Note however that low reverberation levels correspond to situations in
532 which temporal smearing of the target will probably have negligible effect on intelligibility
533 ([Lavandier and Culling, 2008](#)), greatly limiting the interest for the early-late separation to
534 start with. The model version based on short-term IACC gave similar performances to the
535 room-independent version, except for the dataset from [Lavandier and Culling \(2008\)](#). The
536 IACC version then estimated ELL shorter than the room-independent ELL, leading to a
537 large overestimation of the effect of the temporal smearing of the target speech. Note that
538 the method is binaural and could not be tested on the dataset from [Cueille *et al.* \(2022\)](#)
539 also involving high levels of reverberation. Overall the estimated ELLs were always very
540 short for this method (below 12 ms, [Table II](#)). This would imply that only the direct sound
541 is considered useful and most of the early speech reflections (which can increase speech
542 intelligibility) are considered detrimental, which is not appropriate. Overall, the room-
543 independent and Abel versions of the model gave the best predictions and were accurate for
544 all datasets. The Abel version was more accurate than the room-independent version for
545 one dataset with high level of reverberation, but less accurate for another dataset involving
546 a virtual room. Even if [Leclère *et al.* \(2015\)](#) showed that optimizing the ELL as a function
547 of the room/BRIR could improve intelligibility predictions, the room-independent version of
548 the model could be preferred to the Abel version, because it is simpler to implement and has
549 good performance across the wide range of conditions involved in the seven datasets provided
550 here. The Kokabi and IACC versions were not able to describe with enough accuracy all
551 these datasets.

552 The internal noise only affected the predictions for the two datasets involving HI listeners
553 (Cueille *et al.*, 2022; Vicente *et al.*, 2021). The version using the external sound broadband
554 level was slightly more accurate for the dataset from Vicente *et al.* (2021), while the version
555 using the external spectrum was more accurate with the dataset from Cueille *et al.* (2022).
556 The main difference between the two datasets is the degree of hearing loss of the HI listeners,
557 the HI listeners of Cueille *et al.* (2022) having a higher degree of hearing loss. The internal
558 noise taking the external broadband level as input could be too high for the HI listeners with
559 a high degree of hearing loss, while the internal noise using the external spectrum would be
560 too low for the HI listeners with a low degree of hearing loss. This assumption is supported
561 by the individual predictions of the dataset from Cueille *et al.* (2022) (Suppl. Fig. 10¹),
562 which show that considering the external broadband level largely overestimates the SRTs of
563 some of the HI listeners. It is also in agreement with the results of Vicente *et al.* (2020), who
564 found that taking the external broadband level as input allowed the model to give accurate
565 predictions for HI listeners with a low degree of hearing loss. Overall, it appears at this
566 stage that we cannot tell which internal noise calculation method is better. This requires
567 further investigation, considering yet other datasets (Lavandier *et al.*, 2021; Vicente *et al.*,
568 2020).

569 B. Comparison with the original models

570 The *vicente2020* model was inaccurate for the datasets where the speech was temporally
571 smeared, that is to say, Lavandier and Culling (2008), the third experiment of Collin and
572 Lavandier (2013), and Cueille *et al.* (2022). The *leclere2015* model gave inaccurate results

573 for the datasets with modulated noise or HI listeners, that is to say, the first and third
574 experiment of [Collin and Lavandier \(2013\)](#), and [Cueille et al. \(2022\)](#), respectively. These
575 results were expected, as *vicente2020* does not discriminate between early and late target
576 reflections, and *leclere2015* does not take the masker modulation characteristics as input
577 nor the hearing profile of the listener. In contrast, the proposed model gave predictions
578 as accurate as the *vicente2020* model for the datasets with a modulated interferer or HI
579 listeners, and as accurate as the *leclere2015* model for the datasets with a temporally smeared
580 target speech. It was also able to describe the data from [Cueille et al. \(2022\)](#) and the
581 experiment 3 of [Collin and Lavandier \(2013\)](#), something that neither the *vicente2020* nor
582 the *leclere2015* models can do. The proposed model combined the advantages of each
583 original model, so that it extends their performance and generalizability to a larger range
584 of conditions.

585 C. Comparison with other models from the literature

586 The main advantage of the proposed model is that it allows for predictions in a large
587 variety of conditions, taking into account the effects of binaural hearing, hearing impairment,
588 reverberation, and interferer modulations. There exist other binaural models which take into
589 account the effect of hearing impairment by taking the listener’s audiogram as input, such as
590 the one from [Beutelmann et al. \(2010\)](#). This model was tested by [Beutelmann et al. \(2010\)](#)
591 and [Ewert et al. \(2017\)](#) with HI and NH listeners, as well as modulated and stationary
592 noise. However, it cannot take into account the effect of the temporal smearing of the target
593 speech.

594 There also exist other binaural models which allow to predict the effect of the temporal
595 smearing of the target speech caused by reverberation, such as the ones developed by van
596 Wijngaarden and Drullman (2008), Andersen *et al.* (2018) or Rennies *et al.* (2011). However,
597 the models of van Wijngaarden and Drullman (2008) and Andersen *et al.* (2018) work only
598 for NH listeners. The models proposed by Rennies *et al.* (2011) are extensions of the model
599 of Beutelmann *et al.* (2010) which can predict the temporal smearing of the target speech.
600 One of those extensions does an early-late separation of the BRIR similar to the proposed
601 model. Like the original Beutelmann *et al.* (2010) model, these extensions should in principle
602 work for HI listeners and modulated noises. However, to the best of our knowledge, they
603 were so far only tested for NH listeners and stationary noise at several reverberation levels.

604 When tested in different conditions than those considered here, the model from (Beutel-
605 mann *et al.*, 2010) led to similar individual prediction performances than the proposed model,
606 with a correlation of 0.78, and a mean error of 3 dB. The more accurate model version from
607 Rennies *et al.* (2011) gave a correlation of 0.74 and a mean error of 1 dB with the individual
608 predictions. The model from Andersen *et al.* (2018) gave correlations between 0.97 and 0.98
609 with the averaged data of the five datasets they tested. It would be interesting to verify
610 that these models work correctly with HI listeners in reverberant conditions. Furthermore,
611 the performance statistics of these models cannot be directly compared to the ones obtained
612 with the proposed model, as they were obtained with datasets involving other speech mate-
613 rials and different conditions. It could be interesting to test the proposed model along with
614 the models from the literature on the same datasets in order to compare their performances.

615 The models proposed during the Clarity Challenge allow to predict the performances of
616 HI listeners with hearing aids in reverberant conditions (Barker *et al.*, 2022). Some of these
617 models also have the advantage of being non-intrusive, necessitating only the combination of
618 the speech and noise signals at the two ears, while the proposed model requires the separated
619 target and noise signals as well as the target and masker BRIRs as input, limiting its range
620 of application. However, these other models work with a machine learning approach, and
621 necessitate training with speech and listening conditions similar to the evaluation material
622 beforehand. Furthermore, the Clarity Challenge made no clear separation between the
623 training and test materials, which creates the risk that overfitted machine learning models
624 are rewarded.

625 **D. Limitations of the proposed model**

626 The dataset from Cueille *et al.* (2022) is slightly less accurately predicted than the other
627 datasets tested here, with larger prediction errors. This might be partly explained by the
628 external sound level used in the model. During the experiment, the target speech was set
629 at a fixed sound level of 50 dB SPL for the NH listeners, while the interfering noise (which
630 was louder than the speech in most conditions that led to negative SRTs) varied in level
631 depending on the condition. In the model, the external sound level was fixed to the target
632 speech level for all conditions. Even if the higher noise levels would have been a better
633 approximation of the external sound levels at negative SNRs, these levels cannot be used
634 as a model input because they are fixed by the SRT that corresponds to the model output.

635 The use of the target level could have led to an underestimation of the internal noise of the
636 HI listeners in some conditions and affected the predictions.

637 The experiment from [Lavandier and Culling \(2008\)](#) is also not perfectly predicted, with a
638 correlation coefficient of 0.85 between measured and predicted SRTs. The room-independent
639 version of the model underestimates speech intelligibility in the conditions with an anechoic
640 target, and overestimates it in the conditions with a moderately reverberant target. This
641 is similar to the predictions obtained with the original *leclere2015* model. According to
642 the model predictions, this intelligibility increase (SRT decrease) between the anechoic and
643 moderately reverberant conditions would be due to coloration which would have influenced
644 better-ear listening ([Leclère et al., 2015](#)). However, the listeners did not seem to take any
645 advantage of this coloration.

646 The model slightly overestimates the dip listening benefit for the experiment 4 of [Collin
647 and Lavandier \(2013\)](#) and the datasets of [Cueille et al. \(2022\)](#) and [Vicente et al. \(2021\)](#). This
648 is something that was already observed by [Vicente et al. \(2020\)](#). It is likely a misprediction
649 from the better-ear listening component, as the dip listening overestimation is present even
650 in the conditions where there is no binaural unmasking. For example, in the dataset of
651 [Vicente et al. \(2021\)](#), with a target azimuth of 20° , a dip listening benefit of 2.7 dB is
652 observed in the data, while the model predicted a benefit of 4.1 dB, of which 4 dB are due
653 to better-ear listening.

654 For the experiment 4 of [Collin and Lavandier \(2013\)](#) the model overestimates the SRM
655 in the symmetrical condition for the 2-voice modulated maskers. This was already observed

656 with the *vicente2020* model and could be due to binaural sluggishness not being taken into
657 account for the better-ear listening component of the model (Vicente and Lavandier, 2020).

658 Another drawback of the proposed model is its intrusiveness. It needs the separated
659 target and noise signals as well as the target and masker BRIRs as input. As explained
660 above, models such as those of the Clarity Challenge only need the noisy speech signals at
661 the two ears.

662 Furthermore, this model can only predict differences between conditions in a given
663 dataset. As in the *vicente2020* and *leclere2015* models (and all the models originating
664 from the model of Lavandier and Culling (2010)), nothing is implemented to account for the
665 effect of the speech material.

666 Finally, the datasets considered here only allow to test for the individual effects (rever-
667 beration, hearing impairment, SRM, dip listening) in a limited number of combinations.
668 It could be interesting to further test the model with a dataset involving all these effects
669 simultaneously, but this would require a rather large number of tested conditions.

670 V. CONCLUSION

671 A combination of two existing binaural speech intelligibility models is proposed. It allows
672 to predict the effects of hearing loss and temporal smearing of the target speech by rever-
673 beration, along with the effects of SRM and dip listening and the effects of reverberation on
674 these mechanisms. This is done by combining the internal noise function of the *vicente2020*
675 model and the BRIR separation function of the *leclere2015* model. The proposed model
676 gave comparable predictions for two of the four tested methods of BRIR separation: the

677 room-independent version, for which the ELL is fixed to 30 ms (Leclère *et al.*, 2015), and
678 the version for which the ELL is defined as the moment when the diffuse reverberation tail
679 begins (Abel and Huang, 2006). The two other versions based on the IACC (long-term or
680 short-term) were less accurate for at least one of the tested datasets. The room-independent
681 version might be preferable due to its simpler implementation. It gave accurate predictions
682 for seven datasets from the literature, with a Pearson’s coefficient correlation between data
683 and prediction ranging from 0.85 to 0.98, and a mean absolute prediction error always be-
684 low 1.4 dB. The two methods of internal noise calculation which were tested gave similarly
685 accurate predictions. The method developed in the *vicente2020* model was more accurate
686 for HI listeners with a moderate hearing loss, while the new proposed method was more
687 accurate for HI listeners with high hearing loss.

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695 experiments with human participants are taken from previously published studies. The
696 model developed here is being made publicly available within the Auditory Modeling Toolbox

697 (AMT 1.1; Majdak *et al.*, 2022), along with the code, data and signals used to run the model
698 for an example experiment, as done by Lavandier *et al.* (2022).

699 SUPPLEMENTARY MATERIALS

700 See supplementary materials at [URL will be inserted by AIP] for the figures comparing
701 the predictions of the proposed model to those of the *vicente2020* and *leclere2015* models
702 as well as the individual predictions.

703 ¹See supplementary materials at [URL will be inserted by AIP]

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